

High-temperature thermal and mechanical properties of aerogel/fibrous zirconia ceramic composites

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Introduction & Experimental procedure

Introduction: Recently, porous zirconia ceramics for thermal insulation applications have drawn more attention. In addition, aerogels are ideal thermal insulators having ultralow density and ultralow thermal conductivity. Impregnating porous ceramics with aerogels improved the thermal and mechanical properties. However, the above studies were mainly focused on the RT properties, high-T properties of the aerogel/fibrous ceramic composites have not been studied systematically, which are important for high-temperature insulators.

Objectives: Fibrous zirconia ceramics were fabricated using a simple process. The present work aimed at investigating the microstructure, thermal and mechanical properties at high temperatures of the aerogel/fibrous zirconia ceramic composites.

Experimental procedure: Commercial available zirconia fiber with a diameter of 4-7 μm was used as the raw material. Fibrous porous ceramics were fabricated by mixing the zirconia fibers and a binder, followed by vacuum-molding and sintered at 1600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (porosity \approx 85%).

- $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Aldrich was used as the precursor, a mixture of distilled water and ethanol were used as solvent, and propylene oxide was used to initiate the condensation reaction. The solution was introduced into the porous ceramics by vacuum-infiltration. After aging, the alumina aerogel/fibrous ceramic composites were obtained by a supercritical drying process ($T_c=243^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P_c=6.3\text{ MPa}$).
- After the aerogel impregnation, the specimen's density slightly increased from 0.75 to 0.78 g/cm^3 .

Results & discussion

composites after heating at 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30min

High-temperature dimensional stability

- After heating at 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min, the composite had a very small linear shrinkage of 2%.
- The aerogel occupied the pores of the fibrous ceramics, resulting in a significant decrease in pore size. The aerogel's particle size and morphology changed with increasing temperature.
- The growth tendency of the aerogel particles in the composites was much less than that of the monolithic aerogels. This should be due to the better thermal insulation of the fibrous porous ceramic framework compared to air, which suppressed heat transfer to the aerogels in the composites.

Such phenomenon indicates that the aerogels in the composites could maintain structural stability at higher temperatures than the monolithic aerogels.

Insulating properties and mechanical properties

Back-temperature tests for the ceramic sample and the aerogel/ceramic composite

sample	λ_{RT} (W/m·K)
Fibrous ceramics	0.055 ($\rho=0.75$)
the aerogels/ceramic composites	0.046 ($\rho=0.78$)

sample	Compressive strength at RT after 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30min (MPa)	Compressive strength at RT after 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30min (MPa)
Fibrous ceramics	0.9	0.6
the aerogels/ceramic composites	1.1	0.3

Conclusions:

- Impregnating the fibrous zirconia porous ceramics with alumina aerogel is an effective way to improve thermal properties at temperatures up to 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- However, the degradation of mechanical properties after heating at 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ should be considered for thermal insulation applications with load-bearing requirements at high temperatures.